

(DAI), surviving insects were transferred to freshly treated seedlings. Inoculated seedlings were transplanted in seedboxes for disease development. Successive inoculation feeding continued up to 5 d. RTV symptoms were observed at 20 DAI.

GLH survival decreased significantly after 2-d exposure to systemically treated plants. Although survival of GLH exposed to foliar NSB-treated seedlings was not significantly different from check, ability to transmit RTV was significantly lower than that of untreated seedlings (see table).

Survival of GLH females and RTV transmission after 5 d exposure to TN1 rice seedlings treated with 2,500 ppm NSB.^a IRRI, 1987.

Treatment	GLH survival (%)				RTV infection (%)	
	1d	2d	3d	5d	1d	2d
Foliar	95 a	91 b	84 b	69 b	38 b	8 a
Systemic	90 a	74 a	69 a	51 a	17 a	4 a
Check	95 a	89 b	84 b	74 b	65 c	22 a

^aAv of 5 replications, 30 GLH and 30 TN1 seedlings/replication. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Systemic NSB application was best against RTV transmission. RTV transmission efficiency of the vector

became negligible after 2d inoculation feeding in check as well as in treated plants. □

Compatible insecticides and fungicides to control leaf folder (LF) and sheath rot (ShR) in rice

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We studied the compatibility of commonly used insecticides phosphamidon, monocrotophos, and chlorpyrifos with popular fungicides edifenphos, mancozeb, and carbendazim

during 1985-86 and 1986-87. Field trials consisted of 10 treatments replicated 3 times. In both years, 25-d-old Co 43 seedlings were planted in 10-m² plots at 20- × 10-cm spacing. Combined sprays were applied at 20, 40, and 60 d after transplanting.

Only rice LF and ShR occurred during the study. In both years, combined spraying of monocrotophos with any one of the three fungicides was the most effective treatment, keeping LF infestation well below economic injury level (<5%). In 1986-87, combined

spraying of monocrotophos with carbendazim resulted in the lowest incidence of ShR (see table).

In both years, combined spraying of monocrotophos with the three fungicides resulted in the highest yields. □

Efficacy and compatibility of insecticides and fungicides in the control of rice pests and diseases. Rice Research Station, Tirur, India, 1985-86 and 1986-87.

Treatment	1985-86		1986-87		
	LF-damaged leaves (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	LF-damaged leaves (%)	ShR infected tillers (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Phosphamidon 250 ml/ha + edifenphos 500 ml/ha	29	3.1	15	7.0	4.2
Phosphamidon 250 ml/ha + mancozeb 1000 g/ha	19	3.0	14	6.6	4.1
Phosphamidon 250 ml/ha + carbendazim 250 g/ha	32	2.8	16	8.2	3.8
Monocrotophos 500 ml/ha + edifenphos 500 ml/ha	4	3.4	2	6.0	4.5
Monocrotophos 500 ml/ha + mancozeb 1000 g/ha	3	3.6	3	6.0	4.2
Monocrotophos 500 ml/ha + carbendazim 250 g/ha	3	3.2	2	4.9	4.2
Chlorpyrifos 500 ml/ha + edifenphos 500 ml/ha	11	3.1	7	7.0	4.2
Chlorpyrifos 500 ml/ha + mancozeb 1000 g/ha	15	2.8	9	6.2	3.9
Chlorpyrifos 500 ml/ha + carbendazim 250 g/ha	17	2.9	25	5.6	4.0
Control	63	2.7	77	13.5	3.1
CD (P=0.05)	5.0	1.5	15.4	5.5	0.4

Brown planthopper (BPH) outbreak in Thanjavur District, Tamil Nadu

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During the Jun-Sep 1987 drought due to failure of the monsoon, a BPH outbreak in Sivapurani, Kondasamudram, and Kurichi villages of Kumbakonam division, Thanjavur District, caused typical hopperburn symptoms on IR50. Approximately 100 ha were affected. Farmers applied double the recommended N as basal fertilizer. Because the insecticides used were not directed toward the base of the plants, control was inadequate. Furthermore, the farmers sprayed quinalphos, a resurgence causing insecticide, which aggravated the pest population.

Unsprayed fields recorded 56 hoppers/hill; phosphamidon-sprayed fields had 8 hoppers/hill. Where quinalphos was sprayed, populations